

ECONOMIC EFFECT OF HEALTH POLICIES ON NATIONAL GROWTH (1999-2024)

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Abstract: *This study examined the effect of health policies on national growth (1999-2024). The study was a time series thereby employing Secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical bulletin 2024 and World Development Index 2024. The data were subjected to unit root diagnostic test to determine whether they are stationarity or otherwise. The data were integrated of order 1(0) and 1(1). Therefore, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was adopted, the Error Correction Model (ECM) technique was also adopted to check for the cointegration. The study reported a long run relationship between economic growth and health expenditures instruments. The findings of the study reveals that there is a positive relationship between life expectancy rate, unemployment rate and health care ratio per capital on economic growth in Nigeria such that an increase in the value of the identified explanatory variables will lead to increase in economic growth in Nigeria. More so, the result reveals that domestic government health expenditure and domestic private health expenditure have negative relationship on economic growth in Nigeria which implies that an increase in the identified explanatory variables ill lead to decrease in economic growth in Nigeria. The study also reveals that all the explanatory variables (domestic government health expenditure, domestic private health expenditure, life expectancy rate, unemployment rate and health care ratio per capital) has significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study concludes that healthcare expenditures tools influence economic growth in Nigeria and the paper recommends the federal government should enhance individual health spending ability (health insurance may be relevant here), increase budgetary allocation to health sector and monitor the implementation of heath sector budget to achieve sustainable economic growth.*

INTRODUCTION

A wholesome health is crucial to human well-being, a measure of increased productivity and

total economic growth and development. It is also a driving force on which human capitals such as education and skill relied. The positive

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consequence of good health on economic growth gives impetus to the worth of the strength of improvements in human health in the past decades.

The importance of government expenditure in the process of human development is not only improving education also improving the health of people. Health status is conventionally measured by life expectancy at birth, and by child and infant mortality. Neither of these measures reflects the extent of morbidity. Health indicators (nutrition, mobility, morbidity and height) are positively correlated with education (Sackey, 2021). The provision of health is a key element of a policy to promote broad-based economic growth. The main asset of the poor is clearly their labour health services improve the productivity and earnings of workers. The burden of diseases such as HIV/AIDS can slow the economic growth of developing countries. Health is important tools to empower poor people and overcome exclusion based on gender, location and other correlates of poverty.

It is increasingly being recognized that simply allocating greater public resources to basic health services is not enough to ensure that quality services are made available to the vast majority of poor citizens in the developing world. The impact of public spending on actual services in health service delivery depends critically on existing institutions and incentives in the public sector. In recent years, public revenues in Nigeria have increased substantially due to the boom in world oil prices, and some of this

windfall is being channeled into increased spending on primary health care. There remains a concern whether the institutions of public accountability in the country will effectively allow these large spending programs to translate into improved services. Yet, it has been shown that, even after taking note of low levels of these variables, “one would have expected a much higher level of human development achievement in Nigeria where oil export boosted the GDP, human development has continued to decrease since 1981(Gupta, 2021).

The country’s healthcare services have been consistently poor, with a growing population and emerging health inequalities exacerbating the situation. The sector is characterized by lack of adequate health infrastructure, obsolete facilities and insufficient funding to equip and staff hospitals. Prioritizing an equitable and inclusive healthcare system is crucial for governments at all levels, including the national and the sub-national levels, as adequate and appropriate financing of healthcare is imperative for the future of every nation. The share of total federal expenditure for the Federal Ministry of Health, the administrative body responsible for providing quality and efficient health care services for Nigerians, has been hovering between four and five percent for the last four years.

In Nigeria, fluctuating public health expenditure, unemployment rate, low per capita income and population growth may have affected the life expectancy of Nigerians. In 1990

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and 1997, public health expenditure rose from ₦1.03 billion to ₦5.64 billion while life expectancy averaged 45 years within the same period. By 2004, when public health expenditure fell to ₦41.83 billion, from ₦48.87 billion allocated in 2002, life expectancy rose to 47 years. Public health expenditure rose to ₦225.38 billion in 2011 and life expectancy increased to 51 years. The years that followed (2012, 2013 and 2014) had a lower allocation in billions to the health sector (₦222.64, ₦219.29, ₦224.25 respectively) while life expectancy averaged 51 years in 2012 and 2013, then increased to 52 years in 2014. In 2015, public health expenditure increased from ₦278.78 billion to ₦547 billion in 2021, consequently, life expectancy rose from 52 years to 55 years respectively

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Though life expectancy has been increasing over the years, it is still one of the lowest in the world (Ibrahim & Rejoice, 2022). Nigeria's highest allocation to the health sector reached 5.75 per cent an all-time high in 2023 (Tambe, 2022). It is below the required 15 per cent benchmark agreed by the African Union and the World Health Organization benchmark of 18 per cent (Wasiu, 2020). Nigeria may have not met the expected United Nations and African Union requirements due to challenges attributed to insecurity which has bedeviled the economy since 2012 till date. The 5.75 per cent allocation is low considering Nigeria is the seventh most populated country in the world, the unemployment rate is high (37.7 per cent) and

the per capita income (\$2,184), is insufficient to cater for what the government did not subsidize (Tambe, 2022). However, the increase to 5.75 per cent may be a result of health challenges facing the economy (like Monkey pox, Lassa fever and coronavirus). Nevertheless, this increase has not contributed to an increase in life expectancy (55 years) which is the third lowest in the world (Tambe, 2022).

Despite the increase of federal health budget allocations from 434 billion naira in 2018 to 1.02 trillion naira in 2021, the ministry underspent their approved budget by 31 percent in 2018 and 47 percent in 2021. This underspending limits the funding available for the nation's health system and therefore restricts opportunities for equitable, qualitative and universally accessible healthcare, (International Budget Partnership (IBP), 2022) This situation has continually make argument that allocating more public resources to health services is not enough to ensure quality services and economic growth. To examine the validity of this argument, this study investigates the impact of health care budget, financing and interventions using domestic government general health expenditure (% of current health expenditure), domestic private health expenditure (% of current health expenditure) and out-of pocket expenditure (% of current health expenditure), healthcare ratio to Per Capita, healthcare budget expenditure ratio to GDP, immunization intervention rates, inflation and exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria from 1990 - 2023.

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RESEARCH QUESTION

This study will be guided by the following research questions

1. What is the impact of health policies on national growth in Nigeria?
2. What is the long run relationship between health policies and national growth in Nigeria?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine the impact of health policies on national growth in Nigeria?
2. To examine the long run relationship between health policies and national growth in Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. **H₀:** Health policies has no significant impact on national growth in Nigeria
2. **H₀:** There is no long run relationship between health policies and national growth in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

HEALTHCARE EXPENDITURE.

Healthcare financing and expenditures is the mobilization of funds for healthcare services (Oyefabi, Aliyu & Idris, 2023). It is the provision of money, funds or resources to the planned activities of the government to maintain people's health. The amount of resources allocated for health care in a country is said to be a reflection of health value placement in respect of other categories of goods and services. The pattern of health expenditures is thus linked to the

provision of health services. There are various means of health care financing which include tax-based public sector health financing, household out-of-pocket health expenditure, the private sector (donor funding), health insurance among others (Olayiwola, Oloruntuyi & Abiodun, 2022). Government health expenditure is the share of revenues from domestic general government sources spent on health as percentage of current health expenditure indicates how much is funded domestically by the government. Domestic general government sources include government internal transfers and grants, government transfers and subsidies to voluntary schemes, as well as social health insurance contributions (WHO, 2023). An out-of-pocket expense (or out-of-pocket cost, OOP) is the direct payment of money that may or may not be later reimbursed from a third-party source. It is any direct outlay by households, including gratuities and in-kind payments, to health practitioners and suppliers of pharmaceuticals, therapeutic appliances, and other goods and services whose primary intent is to contribute to the restoration or enhancement of the health status of individuals or population groups. It is a part of private health expenditure (WDI, 2022).

ECONOMIC GROWTH

Anyiwe and Oziegbe (2023) opined that economic growth connotes increase in outputs in various sectors, national product, and national income, improved level of technology, health, education and urbanization. In addition,

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economic growth refers to as a long term rise in its capacity to supply increasingly diverse economic goods to its population. It is also a process by which the productive capacity of the economy is increased over time to bring about rising level of national output and income. On the other hand, economic growth is a long term process wherein the substantial and sustained rise in real national income, total population and real per capita income takes place. In addition, economic growth is the expansion of the system in one or more dimensions without a change in its structure. Thus economic growth is related to a quantitative, sustained increase in the country s per capita output or income accompanied by expansion in its labour force, consumption, capital and volume of trade (Ukwueze, 2022).

PUBLIC HEALTH EXPENDITURE

The concept of public health expenditure has been defined by several scholars including Admane and Sliman (2021), Omoloba (2020) and Bashir (2016). The common denominator in all their conceptualizations is that public health expenditure are monetary government allocations to the health sector to improve, maintain and restore the health status of citizens within a given period. For the sake of this study, public health expenditure will be defined as all government spending on health to develop human health status and increase the life expectancy of the population. The definition is deemed suitable because it includes the major variables (public health expenditure and life expectancy) in the study.

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LIFE EXPECTANCY

Several scholars have conceptualized life expectancy. This can be traced to Clarkson (2022), Cameron, Contreras and Cornwell (2019) and Stout (2018) who agree that life expectancy is the mean age that people in a given environment will be at the time of death given their diet, heredity, profession, physical disorder and genetic ability to survive diseases. This study defines life expectancy as the number of years an individual will survive in an environment given the population size, health services provided by the government and the individual's ability to afford a healthy lifestyle based on his income. The study considers this definition appropriate because it highlights some variables (population growth, per capita income and public health expenditure) considered in the study.

PER CAPITA INCOME

Per capita income has been conceptualized Orekoya (2022) as the average income earned by each person in a specific area. It is determined by dividing total income of the area by the population in the area. This study defines per capita income as the average income earned by each individual in a specific population or group, typically calculated on an annual basis. It aids in measuring the well-being and standard of living of the population.

UNEMPLOYMENT RATE

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Jajere (2016) view unemployment rate as the ratio of individuals who are within the work force and are actively looking for employment but are unable to find gainful employment. This study defines unemployment rate as the percentage of economically active population who are unemployed due to inadequate resources in the economy and poor health status of the citizens, despite the prevailing wage rate.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

GROSSMAN'S THEORY OF HEALTH DEMAND

This theory was propounded by Grossman (1972). The theory states that health capital is a good which can be consumed or invested in. Health capital can be inherited and if not developed, depreciates. Health is consumed because it increases the quality of work and leisure while health can be increased by investing in health facilities, education and food. The theory explains that health is treated as a capital stock for people to produce more health capital by investing in health. The relationship between health consumption and health investment explains the connection among health-related outcomes and decisions which affect the life expectancy of the population. Life expectancy improves over time as a result of individual decisions. These decisions are affected by the cost of healthcare services. The theory recognizes that individuals aim at maximizing utility subject to constraint. Individuals' demand for healthcare services is constrained by the price of healthcare services and per capita income.

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Prices of healthcare services are determined by the government and private sector. Many government-owned healthcare facilities provide healthcare services as a public good at subsidized rates. The subsidy attracts many individuals who have low per capita income and cannot afford the prices of healthcare services provided by the private sector. Investment by the government in the health sector is vital for longevity of the population as many individuals patronize government-owned health facilities (Ibrahim & Rejoice, 2022). The theory is adopted because of its relevance to this study in the sense that, it explains government investment in health and health-related outcomes (life expectancy).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Many empirical studies had established direct causal relationship between health financing and economic growth in various economy in the world.

Yusuf (2022) Used ARDL model to determine health expenditure where HDI is a composite index that measures a country's overall development based on three key dimensions: life expectancy at birth; mean years of schooling and expected years of schooling; per capita income or Gross National Income (GNI) per capita. Increasing capital expenditure in the health sector can lead to improvements in health indicators, such as increased life expectancy and reduced infant mortality rates. The findings show that improvements contribute positively to the health dimension of the HDI. Better healthcare can lead to improved school

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attendance and cognitive development among children, indirectly contributing to the education dimension of the HDI. A healthier population can be more productive, which can positively affect the standard of living dimension of the HDI.

Awogbemi (2023) Using VECM, concluded that there is a clear and evident link between the health sector expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria, and recommends private sector investment in health and education to increase their involvement in the delivery of human capital services to the populace. This assumes that government spending on the health sector is ineffective in addressing health challenges without private investment in health. Also, an increase in the welfare programs for health care workers in order to lower the misery index in Nigeria and prevent a mass flight of doctors and other health professionals from the country's shores is important as this would improve the quality of life for Nigerians.

Akintunde et al. (2022), determined public health expenditure and health outcomes in Nigeria using Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model. The study also shows the existence of a long-run relationship between health expenditure and economic growth for both Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC) countries and the five other countries that achieved the 2001 Abuja declaration. Bi-directional causality between economic growth and health expenditure was also noticed for CEMAC countries while

countries that achieved the 2001 Abuja declaration portrayed a unilateral causality running from economic growth to health expenditure. This implies that income is an essential component in explaining health care expenditure, hence, increase in level of income can stimulate growth of health expenditure.

Ojo and Ojo (2022) discovered that government expenditure on education and health had a positive and significant impact on economic growth in their study on health expenditure, education, and economic growth in Nigeria using the error correlation model (ECM) as an estimating approach. The result of the study tallies with the recent findings of Ibrahim and Rejoice (2022). Applying ARDL model, Wasiu (2020) studied the link connecting government health financing and outcomes of health in Nigeria from 1985 to 2019. The study found that government health financing significantly and positively affects life expectancy. Other findings showed that though the urban population is significant it has a negative relationship with life expectancy while corruption and life expectancy have a positive relationship though the effect is not significant. From 1979 to 2012, Oluwatoyin, Folasade and Fagbeminiyi (2021) utilized Johansen Cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) technique to examine the effect of health spending by government on outcome of health in Nigeria. The study revealed that government health expenditure is significant in explaining life expectancy though the relationship is negative.

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Focusing on 45 countries from different sub-regions, Abdul-ganiyu and Tijjani (2021) studied how life expectancy is affected by health expenditure from 2000-2020. Fixed effects estimation method and two-stage least squares were employed as techniques of analysis. The study revealed that in West Africa when the Fixed Effect Method was applied, health expenditure and life expectancy had a positive relationship but an inverse relationship exists between life expectancy and spending on health in Southern and Central Africa, while in Northern and Eastern parts of Africa, health expenditure did not affect life expectancy. When the two-stage least square technique was applied the result revealed that it is only in Central Africa that fluctuations in life expectancy can be attributed to spending on health. There is a need for a more current study in order to capture government spending as a result of recent health crises (coronavirus) that affected many countries' life expectancy.

METHODOLOGY

MODEL SPECIFICATION

A healthier workforce is likely to raise better wages by minimizing inefficiencies. Improving the workforce's health increases productivity and raises the minimum wage through presenteeism at work and overtime incentives while reducing potential losses. More recently, the effect of health as measured by life expectancy at birth on economic growth portrays that health's elasticity of growth is positive and significant. Bakare & Olubokun (2004), high

government expenditure on the health sector stimulates economic production because a healthy person is more likely to produce at a higher rate than an unhealthy person. Increased income would lead to high human capital via an increase in health expenditure which in turn, lead to increased productivity.

The model in this paper is specified in a functional form as follows:

$$RGDP = f (DGHE, DPHE, LER, UNEMPR, HCRPCI). \quad (1)$$

Therefore, equation (1) may be expressed in a linear and log form as:

$$LGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1LDGHE_t + \beta_2LDPHE_t + \beta_3LER_t + \beta_4UNEMPR_t + \beta_5HCRPCI_t + \mu \quad (2)$$

Where,

LGDP = Log value of Gross Domestic Product

LDGHE = Log value of Domestic Government Expenditure on Health

LDPHE = Log value of Domestic Private Health Expenditure

LER = life expectancy rate

UNEMPR = Unemployment Rate

HCRPCI = health Care Ratio Per Capital Income

SOURCE OF DATA

The study is an ex-post factor research. The variables for the study were based on secondary data. The data were sourced from CBN Statistical bulletin, 2024 edition and world Development Index (WDI 2024). The time series covers the market based economic era when health economic budgets, financing and interventions were seen to be the main stand-post of economies across the world. Thus, the data

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covers 1999 to 2024. This study employs annual data on the domestic general health expenditure (CBN, 2024), Domestic private health expenditure (WDI, 2024,), health care ratio to Per Capita (CBN), Health expenditure ratio to GDP (CBN, 2023), immunization intervention (WDI), inflation (CBN, 2024), and Life expectancy rate (CBN, 2024), as the explanatory

variables and the Gross Domestic Product (CBN, 2024) as the proxy for economic growth as the dependent variable.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.

Result Presentation Data analysis using descriptive statistics were carried out and the results were presented on Table 1

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics Results

	RGDP	DGHE	DPHE	LER	UNEMPR	HCRPC
Mean	4.697059	15.79765	61.46500	73.43706	98.76471	4.126471
Median	4.200000	15.35000	67.11500	64.80000	67.00000	3.900000
Maximum	15.30000	26.90000	80.14000	551.3000	1615.000	8.600000
Minimum	0.10000	11.02000	36.92000	37.00000	15.00000	2.490000
Std. Dev.	3.347589	4.556428	14.67634	85.65711	269.6561	1.149379
Skewness	1.071766	0.867886	-0.187873	5.320436	5.456300	2.032761
Kurtosis	4.406707	3.076199	1.275475	30.24933	31.21226	8.127282
Jarque-Bera	9.312539	4.276507	4.413162	1212.319	1296.273	60.65810
Probability	0.009502	0.117860	0.110076	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	159.7000	537.1200	2089.810	2496.860	3358.000	140.3000
Sum Sq. Dev.	369.8097	685.1142	7108.034	242125.6	2399576	43.59538
Observations	34	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Author's Computation 2025 using E-views 9.0

Table 1 above contain summary of statistics: the mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, Kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera values for the variables under consideration. It shows the mean value of LRGDP, DGHE, DPHE, LER, UNEMPR, and HCRPC are 4.6, 15.7, 61.4, 73.4, 98.7, and 4.1, respectively. UNEMPR has the

highest level of discrepancy, as shown in the standard deviation result (269.65). This means that unemployment rate was found to be more volatile and unpredictable having the highest standard deviation of 269.6561. Healthcare care ratio per Capital (HCRPC) shows the lowest level with the standard deviation of 1.149379

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respectively. Skewness is a measure of the rate of asymmetry or discrepancy of the variables. The p-value of the JarqueBera test indicated that most of the series are normally distributed.

TESTING FOR STATIONARITY

Following the Granger and Newbold (1977), most time series variables are non - stationary, and utilizing such non - stationary variables in

estimation might lead to spurious regression. To overcome this shortcoming, the stationary status of the series using both the Augmented DickeyFuller (ADF) was utilized. The ADF test is based on minimizing the Akaike information criterion (AIC). The bandwidth is selected based on the Newey-west approach.

TABLE 2: UNIT ROOT TEST RESULTS (ADF STATISTICS)

Statistics	Statistics at level		Statistics at 1st difference		Integration Order
	ADF	Critical value @5%	ADF	Critical value @5%	
RGDP	-2.413056	-2.967767	-11.02635	-2.957110	I(1)
LDGHE	-1.973339	-2.954021	-5.512444	-2.960411	I(1)
LDPHE	-1.729811	-2.954021	-5.860955	-2.957110	I(1)
LER	-1.011168	-2.967767	-4.982374	-2.967767	I(1)
UNEMPR	-4.958045	-2.954021	-28.27675	-2.957110	I(0)
HCRPC	-4.020956	-2.954021	-9.946343	-2.957110	I(0)

Source: Author's Computation 2025 using E-views 9.0

Results on Table 2 show that the growth rate of real gross domestic product (RGDP), domestic government health expenditure (LDPHE), domestic private health expenditure (LDPHE), and Life expectancy rate (LER) were all stationary at first difference and therefore integrated of order I(1). The unit root results also shows that unemployment rate (UNEMPR,) and health care ratio per capital (HCRPC) were all stationary at level and therefore integrated of order I (0).

AUTOREGRESSIVE DISTRIBUTED LAG (ARDL) BOUND TEST RESULT

The long run dynamic relationship among the variables in the model was tested using the ARDL modelling approach in line with Pesaran and Pesaran (1997) procedure. Table 3 above shows the bounds test. The F-statistics is 4.530237 exceeds the upper bound values at 1 per cent, 2.5 per cent, 5 per cent and 10 per cent critical values. Thus as seen from the above bound test, the f-statistic value of 4.530237 is

evidently above the I (0) and I (1) critical values bound. Our analysis of this series indicates that we reject Ho: that there is no equilibrating

relationship and conclude that there is equilibrating relationship.

TABLE 3: BOUNDS TEST OF PRESENCE OF CO-INTEGRATION IN ARDL INCLUDING THE CRITICAL LOWER AND UPPER BOUND VALUES FOR THE PERIODS

Significance	Lower Bound I(0)	Upper Bound I(1)
10%	1.95	3.06
5%	2.22	3.39
2.5%	2.48	3.7
1%	2.79	4.1
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-Statistic	4.530237	8

Source: Author's Computation 2025 using E-views 9.0

ERROR CORRECTION AND LONG RUN RESULTS.

As observed in table 2, the computed F- statistics of the Bounds Cointegration Test was greater than the F-Critical values at both 10% and 5% level of significance. The implication is that there

is Cointegration among the variables. Thus, the dynamic short-run relationship can be represented with an Error Correction Model (ECM). The estimated ECM and the long-run coefficients are presented in table 4 below.

TABLE 4: LONG-RUN DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

D/ Variable : RGDP	ARDL	(2,2,0,0,2,2,2,2,2)		
Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob
LDGHE	-2.904050	1.273862	-2.279721	0.0486
LDPHE	-2.849563	1.104100	-2.580892	0.0297
LER	1.232111	0.345609	3.565046	0.0061
UNEMPR	3.811832	1.650237	2.309807	0.0462
HCRPC	1.903309	0.644478	2.953255	0.0161
C	5.094464	22.27486	2.287091	0.0480
CointEq(-1)	-1.039935	0.345761	-3.007672	0.0148
R-squared	0.927247			

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Adjusted R-squared	0.749406			
S.E. of regression	0.208593			
Sum squared resid	0.391598			
Log likelihood	25.04603			
F-statistic	5.213923			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.007257			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.403562			

Source: Author's Computation 2025 using Eviews 9.0

DIAGNOSTIC TEST

In order to ascertain if a model is robust, it is expected that the error term be identical, independent and normally distributed with a zero mean and constant variance. Thus, in order

to test for the robustness of the model the study conducted the diagnostic test, to check for the presence of heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation respectively.

TABLE 5: HETEROSKEDASTICITY AND SERIAL CORRELATION TESTS

Heteroskedasticity: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey				Autocorrelation : Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-Statistics	1.344067	Prob.F(22,9)	0.3339	F-Statistics	0.338814	Prob.F(2,7)	0.7237
Obs*R-Squared	24.53296	Prob. Chi-Square (22)	0.3199	Obs*R-Squared	2.824322	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.2436
Scale explained SS	2.810790	Prob. Chi-Square (22)	1.0000				

Source: Author's computation (2024) using Eviews 9.0.

The result from Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity and from Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test revealed that there is no problem of heteroskedasticity and serial correlation respectively

CONCLUSION

This study examines the impact of health budget, financing and interventions on economic growth in Nigeria with data from 1990 to 2023. The

result of the unit root test favoured the use of Auto-regressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) estimation technique. The results show that there is a positive relationship between life expectancy rates, unemployment rate and health care ratio per capital on economic growth in Nigeria such that an increase in the value of the identified explanatory variables will lead to increase in economic growth in Nigeria. More so,

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the result reveals that domestic government health expenditure and domestic private health expenditure have negative relationship on economic growth in Nigeria which implies that an increase in the identified explanatory variables will lead to decrease in economic growth in Nigeria.

The study also reveals that all the explanatory variables (domestic government health expenditure, domestic private health expenditure, life expectancy rate, unemployment rate and health care ratio per capita) has significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

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1. Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from this study, we recommend that government should increase budgetary allocation to health sector and monitor the expenditure therein to achieve sustainable economic growth.

2. Similar, Government should increase employment generation in Nigeria. This will increase the standard of living of its citizens.

3. The anti-graft agencies established to fight corruption should be independent as stipulated by law without any form of favouritism and nepotism in discharging their duties. A well-functioning antigraft agency will enhance proper utilization of public health funds and expenditures.

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